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MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNANCE GAPS IN RENEWABLE ENERGY PROJECTS IN PORTUGAL

Urban Licensing Challenges and Policy Recommendations for Municipalities

HIGHLIGHTS

- Cities play a key role in achieving climate neutrality and must shift towards more sustainable energy systems.
- Positive Energy Districts (PEDs), while providing greater potential for accelerating a just transition, face a series of challenges, ranging from technological and technical ones to social, economic, governance and legal barriers.
- As PEDs rely on renewable energy production, attention should be paid to the legal aspects of renewable energy projects, particularly licensing procedures.
- Lack of a common vision and diverging interests between different levels of governance could hinder long-term strategies for advancing renewable energy projects.
- In Portugal, there are contradictions between, on one hand, national, regional and EU strategies pointing towards a low-carbon future, and, on the other, municipal approaches that demonstrate opposition to renewable energy projects.
- Municipalities should ensure alignment of municipal plans with national, regional and EU strategies; respect the limits established by Decree-Law No. 30-A/2022 and Decree-Law No. 72/2022 and strengthen consistency and predictability in licensing procedures.

BACKGROUND

The energy transition is central to the European Union's goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2050. Cities play a key role in this process, accounting for approximately 75% of global primary energy consumption and around 60% of global greenhouse gas emissions. Consequently, urban areas must shift from fossil fuel-based energy systems towards sustainable models that are low-carbon, efficient, flexible, and socially inclusive.

Within this context, and under the umbrella of the EU's Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan, the Positive Energy Districts (PED) Programme was launched to support the planning, deployment and replication of 100 PEDs across the EU, including in Portugal. The programme is implemented through JPI Urban Europe and the Driving Urban Transitions (DUT) Partnership.

PEDs can be defined as connected urban areas that optimize local renewable energy production, energy efficiency and flexibility, thereby contributing to sustainable urban development and climate neutrality.

However, their implementation faces multidimensional challenges, including technical, financial, socioeconomic, cultural, governance and legal barriers.

The PERSIST project seeks to better understand how socio-economic, socio-cultural and socio-political factors shape PEDs and interact with technological, regulatory and investment frameworks across different geographical, economic and cultural contexts.

Therefore, PERSIST is well positioned to provide recommendations to decision-makers and key stakeholders on how to address these challenges and enable the effective deployment of PEDs in Portugal.

STATEMENT OF THE ISSUE

While PEDs are promoted at the EU level, their effective development requires the involvement of a diverse set of stakeholders — including citizens, city administrations, the real estate sector and energy suppliers — as well as the adaptation of policy frameworks and financial instruments at national, regional and local levels.

Among the challenges to this development, both the scientific literature and research conducted within the PERSIST project identify the lack of a common vision and the existence of diverging interests among stakeholders, which can hinder coherent and long-term strategies enabling PEDs.

This challenge is also evident in the Portuguese context, particularly with regard to the integration of renewable energy systems, which constitute a core functional component of PEDs.

Ideally, PEDs should rely on local and regionally produced renewable energy, enabling substantial reductions in greenhouse gas emissions through the replacement of fossil-fuel based technologies.

On the one hand, national and EU-level strategies promote and incentivize renewable energy projects and aim to streamline licensing procedures. On the other, some municipalities adopt an approach of clear opposition to renewable energy, which end up creating barriers to licensing renewable energy projects, and, consequently, to the operationalization of PEDs in Portugal.

Given this context, this policy brief aims to give an overview of the legal framework that governs urban licensing of renewable energy projects in Portugal; identify the existing contradictions between different levels of governance; and, subsequently, propose recommendations to municipalities aimed at ensuring greater coherence and alignment in urban licensing renewable energy projects.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Urban licensing for renewable energy projects in Portugal

As previously stated, PEDs should ultimately rely on renewable energy production. Thus, it is important to take into account that renewable energy projects must comply with national law, notably with licensing requirements.

In Portugal, the installation of electricity-producing centers based on renewable energy sources, energy storage facilities, Production Units for Self-Consumption (UPACs), and installations for the production of hydrogen through water electrolysis is typically a multi-stage process.

These installations may be subject to multiple licensing procedures, including environmental licensing, urban licensing, and electrical licensing.

The focus of this policy brief is on urban licensing, which refers to the prior control exercised by municipalities over urban operations necessary for renewable energy projects.

Considering European and national commitments on renewable energy and aiming at administrative simplification, Portugal adopted Decree-Law No. 72/2022, which amended Decree-Law No. 30-A/2022, simplifying procedures for prior control of urban operations connected to renewable energy projects. This is an exceptional and temporary regime, extended until 31 December 2026.

Under this regime, two main categories of urban operations emerge:

A. Renewable energy projects with installed capacity greater than 1MW: a procedure for prior control is implemented, which includes a **prior communication**, which allows the works to begin without any express licensing decision, provided the municipality has not expressly rejected the renewable energy project within a deadline.

B. Renewable energy projects with installed capacity equal to or less than 1MW: these installations are exempt from prior control of urban operations, subject only to **prior notification** (information) to the municipality.

Through the provisions of Decree-Law No. 72/2022, there was a recognition that the urban operations for renewable energy projects are simple and can be subject to a more simplified treatment, ensuring greater speed in the licensing procedure without compromising the compliance with applicable legal and regulatory standards.

The role of territorial management instruments on renewable energy projects

Territorial management instruments play a particularly relevant role in urban licensing for renewable energy projects in Portugal, notably through programmes and plans.

Programmes define the strategic framework for territorial development. Plans establish concrete choices regarding spatial planning, territorial organization and land use.

The development of renewable energy is clearly recognized in national programmes, which are aligned with European objectives and enshrine commitments to accelerating the energy transition.

Notable examples include the National Spatial Planning Policy Programme, the National Energy and Climate Plan 2030, and the Roadmap for Carbon Neutrality 2050.

These commitments are also reflected in Regional Spatial Planning Programmes, which reinforce the need to integrate renewable energy production into urban planning. In Portugal, such programmes require municipalities to identify in their Municipal Master Plans suitable areas for renewable energy projects, promote the diversification of energy sources, and encourage local production and energy communities.

Municipal plans remain the key instruments responsible for delimiting areas allocated to renewable energy projects. Only these plans are binding to private parties, which means they are the only ones that can base decisions on the approval or rejection of urban operations.

Contradictions between municipalities' approaches and national and EU commitments towards renewable energies

Empirical findings show that several municipalities in Portugal have adopted restrictive approaches and, in some cases, have effectively prohibited the deployment of renewable energy projects within their territories.

These practices include, for example:

- The creation of disincentivizing mechanisms, such as the imposition of specific municipal fees for the installation of photovoltaic solar systems;
- The requirement of additional formalities for urban operations related to renewable energy projects — such as the submission of a

declaration of municipal interest — even in circumstances where such installations are exempt from prior urban control under national law.

Given this context, it is essential to clarify the limits of municipal intervention. While municipalities may, through their Municipal Master Plans, establish restrictions on the deployment of renewable energy projects within their territories, such restrictions must be duly justified.

General prohibitions or disincentives to renewable energy — particularly when driven only by political opposition to these activities — exceed municipal competences and are inconsistent with higher-level territorial management instruments, as well as with national law and EU strategies on climate and energy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In Portugal, Municipalities play a key role in achieving European and national renewable energy objectives and, consequently, in implementing innovative solutions to accelerate the energy transition, such as Positive Energy Districts.

Thus, the following recommendations are proposed for the Municipalities, in order to ensure a greater alignment of their approaches related to licensing of renewable energy projects with the EU and national goals on the energy transition:

1 Ensure alignment of municipal plans with national and EU renewable energy strategies

Municipalities should review, and where necessary, revise their Municipal Master Plans and related regulations to ensure consistency with regional, national and EU strategies on renewable energies.

Thus, provisions in Municipal Master Plans that impose generic prohibitions or disproportionate restrictions on renewable energy projects should be avoided and, if existing, reviewed. Material constraints to these projects – such as prohibitions in areas of ecological sensitivity – must be concrete, evidence-based and proportionate.

Plus, Municipal Master Plans must, on the other hand, properly locate areas with greater potential for renewable energy projects, classifying areas specifically for this purpose or identifying them as compatible uses.

2 Respect the limits of urban prior control established by national law

Municipalities should strictly observe the simplified procedure for urban licensing of renewable energy projects established by Decree-Law No. 72/2022 and Decree-Law No. 30-A/2022, including the exemption from prior control for renewable energy projects with installed capacity of 1MW or less.

The introduction of additional formal requirements in these hypotheses should be avoided, as it undermines legal certainty, contradicts the purpose of simplification for licensing renewable energy projects and may deter the development of small-scale and community-based renewable energy projects.

3 Strengthen consistency and predictability in licensing procedures

Municipalities should adopt clear and transparent criteria for licensing urban operations in the context of renewable energy projects.

In this sense, guidelines, internal administrative instructions and/or trainings could facilitate consistent decision-making, reduce discretionary or *ad hoc* practices that might undermine, without justification, the development of renewable energy projects.

RECOMMENDED SOURCES

On the PERSIST project:

About PERSIST. <https://www.uc.pt/persist/about-persist/>.

PERSIST – Positive EneRgy diStrlctS driven by citizens.

https://zenodo.org/communities/persit_dut/records.

On the simplification of the urban licensing of renewable energy projects:

Oliveira, F. P. (2025). Do oito ao oitenta nos procedimentos de control urbanístico: evolução dos procedimentos e a comunicação prévia do artigo 4.º-A do Decreto-Lei n.º 30-A/2022 como exemplo de “máxima simplificação e de mínimo controlo”. In: *Estudos em Homenagem ao Conselheiro Presidente João Caupers* (pp. 451-477). Almedina.

On further guidance for Municipalities:

Driving Urban Transitions (DUT) Partnership for SET Plan IWG 3.2 (2025). *PED Framework 3.0: A policy guide to advance Positive Energy Districts in Europe*. <https://dutpartnership.eu/news/ped-framework-30-policy-guide-advance-positive-energy-districts-europe>.

Direção-Geral do Território (2020). *Boas práticas para os Planos Diretores Municipais*. CNT. https://cnt.dgterritorio.gov.pt/sites/default/files/Guia_PDM-GO.pdf

Oliveira, F. P., Mello, B., Farinha, M., Teixeira, N., Roleta, C., Cardoso, A., Valença, C., Geraldés, M., Sena, P. & Ferro, S. (2026). *Guia Municipal para o Licenciamento de Projetos de Energia Renovável*. EMER. https://emer.gov.pt/wp-content/uploads/2026/03/Guia-municipal_EMER_17-03.pdf.

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